

Designing an Online Case-Based Library for Technology Integration in Teacher Education

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Abstract : The purpose of this paper is to introduce an interactive online case-study library website developed in a national project. The design goal of the website is to provide interactive, enhanced, case-based and online educational resource for educators through the purpose and within the scope of a national project. The ADDIE instructional design model was used in the development of the website for interactive case-based library. This library is developed on a web-based platform, which is important in terms of manageability, accessibility, and updateability of data. Users are able to sort the displayed case-studies by their titles, dates, ratings, view counts, etc. The usability test is used and the expert opinion is taken for the evaluation of the website. This website is a tool to integrate technology into education. It is believed that this website will be beneficial for pre-service and in-service teachers in terms of their professional developments.

Keywords : ADDIE, case-based library, design, technology integration

Conference Title : ICET 2014 : International Conference on Educational Technology

Conference Location : Amsterdam, The Netherlands

Conference Dates : August 07-08, 2014